

JBIMA Editorial

Dr Sharif Kaf Al-Ghazal, Editor in Chief

Assalamo Alaikom

The recent junior doctors' strike has been on everyone's minds recently and coupled with the industrial action taken by nurses has highlighted the precarious situation many healthcare professionals are in. And whilst the decision to strike is never an easy one, it is understandable and demands for better working conditions, fairer contracts, and most importantly better patient safety must be heard.

BIMA is heavily involved in advocacy work, with the work done on promoting the Covid vaccine campaign to mosques and the Muslim community and highlighting the positives of organ donation just being a couple of examples of this in recent months. This journal regularly asks for papers detailing advocacy work being done by healthcare professionals so it goes without saying that we defend the right of BIMA's members to advocate for their rights.

As doctors, patient safety is our *raison d'être*. It is our main purpose and mission statement. We cannot deliver effective healthcare to patients if the surrounding environment is not conducive to patient safety, and genuine concerns over the proposed changes to junior doctors' contracts which compromise their ability to provide safe and quality care to those who need it. The oft quoted saying "you can't pour from an empty cup" is relevant here. If doctors are exhausted and constantly fire fighting on the wards with rest between shifts being short in addition to real-term pay cuts, their predicament is clear to see.

The industrial action has also highlighted the ongoing issue of underfunding and understaffing within the NHS. The NHS has long faced challenges in terms of funding and staffing, with reports of overcrowded hospitals, long waiting times, and burnout among healthcare workers. Junior doctors, as frontline healthcare professionals, are acutely aware of these challenges, as they often work in overburdened hospitals with inadequate resources. Advocating for increased funding and staffing levels to

ensure that the NHS can continue to provide high-quality care to patients in a sustainable manner is a worthy cause.

Finally, I would also like to bring to your attention BIMA's Annual National Conference which will be taking place on Saturday 8th July. The theme is "Unity in Community – Winning as One". The conference will explore a wide range of topics and themes and sessions will seek to bring healthcare professionals together. It is not to be missed, and the events team have been working hard to organize it with academic, clinical, wellness and spirituality and personal development sessions being hosted. It will be a great opportunity to listen to leading experts in various medical fields and reflect on their experiences as well as a chance for members to network and get to know one another. The poster presentation session will be particularly useful for the medical students who would like to showcase their work. Good and suitable posters, will inshaAllah be published in this journal.

Very best wishes,

Wassalam.

Dr Sharif Kaf Al-Ghazal
JBIMA, Editor in Chief